

LINGUO SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF TERMS OF TOURISM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8429682>

Annotation: in this article investigated and analyzing the comparative typology of terms of tourism in English, Russian and Uzbek. It is devoted to the comparative study of tourist terminology systems in English and Uzbek through Russian: tour operator, caravanning, familiarization tour, booking, travel fair, travel agent, tourist service provider, resort, motorhome, transportation, etc.

Key words: tour operator, area, familiarization tour, hosting, travel fair, travel agent, tourist service provider, resort, guest.

The most significant laws and decrees about strategic and structural development of tourism signed by the president of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromanovich Mirziyayev in our country, such as, on the 5th of January, 2019, the regulatory acts important for the tourism sphere were approved – the Decree by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №5611 “*On the supplementary measures on the accelerated tourism development in the Republic of Uzbekistan*” and the Resolution by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № 4095 from 2019/01/05 “*On the measures on the accelerated development of the tourism sphere*” and etc. In these regulatory acts the main strategic directions of the tourism sphere development of Tourism in Uzbekistan.

We know that tourism emerged in that period of development of society, when a person got the opportunity to think not only about satisfying primary, vital needs, but also about rest. Although people have always traveled, only at a certain stage of the economic development of society, with the growing need for travel, there appeared persons and institutions that provide them, which led to the formation of a special type of product - tourist services.

Since any terminology is part of the general lexical-semantic system of the language, it contains all the derivational processes inherent in vocabulary in general, namely: lexical, semantic, morphological, syntactic, within the framework of this paragraph, we will focus on considering the semantic method of term formation, since, firstly, tourist terms are often used outside the scientific context, and, secondly, most of them are formed from the words of the general literary language. Thus, the terminology of tourism turns out to be closely related by the relations of semantic derivation with the corresponding words of the general literary language used in the texts of journalistic, colloquial and official-business style. Analyzing the semantic side of the formation of a term, many researchers distinguish three main stages. The current stage in the development of linguistic science is characterized by a deep interest in the description of sublanguages serving professional communities: the number of both theoretical and applied terminology studies is increasing every year. Currently, using the material of various languages, the authors investigate the specific features of scientific texts, the structure of terms and ways of their formation, the issues of standardization and ordering of terminology.

Especially, in the works of this direction, there is still no unity in the goals, principles and methods of research, since they are mainly aimed at solving individual particular problems of comparative terminology.

We know that tourism emerged in that period of development of society, when a person got the opportunity to think not only about satisfying primary, vital needs, but also about rest. Although people have always traveled, only at a certain stage of the economic development of society, with the growing need for travel, there appeared persons and institutions that provide them, which led to the formation of a special type of product - tourist services. Further, tourism became a separate branch of the national economy, which required the formation of an appropriate industry, the availability of qualified personnel, etc. All this necessitated the isolation of a whole layer of lexical units into an independent terminology system.

So, the tourism business continues to develop over time; contacts between Uzbek and foreign partners, who are forced to use tourist terminology, are becoming more active; All travelers are also constantly faced with the need to understand the terms used in the field of tourist services. The science of tourism is also developing rapidly; new specialties of the tourist profile have been allocated in the education system. All this draws attention to the terminology of tourism and gives rise to controversy about it, which is the subject of a lot of publications.

We pointed that even the question of the terms "tourist" and "sayyoh" turned out to be controversial: professionals in the tourist business, as a rule, use the form "tourist", while the authors of popular literature for tourists use the term "tourist". According to L.P. Katlinskaya, it is preferable to use the term "tourist" due to both internal, proper linguistic prerequisites and statistical survey data. Official documents, state standards, federal laws also speak in favor of this term.

In this regard, as well as taking into account the traditions of classical domestic tourism and the traditions of the National Academy of Tourism, in this work we will use the term "tourist". From all that has been said, it follows that the term "tourism" is a fact of mass communication, and its study is the most important condition for successful professional activity and travel organization.

Firstly, organized tourism cannot exist without organizations involved in the compilation and sale of tours, as well as the preparation and conduct of excursions, according to which the following thematic groups can be distinguished within the microfield "organization of tourism": 1) participants and organizers of tourism: host - host, autotourist - motorist, tour operator - tour operator, retailer - retailer, supplier of tourism services - supplier, tour leader - tour leader; 2) types and forms of tourism: all-inclusive tour - all-inclusive tour, caravanning - caravanning, cultural and educational tourism - cultural tourism, familiarization tour - familiarization tour, health tourism - health tourism; 3) organizational processes: booking - booking, tourist route - itinerary, meeting and seeing off - meet and greet, pick-up point, route change - rerouting, cancellation of the tour - tour cancellation; 4) travel documentation: agency agreement - agency agreement, coupon - travel coupon, traveller's check - traveler's check, voucher - voucher, 5) realization, advertising and promotion of a tourist product: tourist catalog - travel catalog, tourist fair - travel fair, travel - travelogue, tourist brochure - tourist brochure.

Many researchers, when considering the nature of a term, talk about its properties, signs and requirements for it. At the same time, the same characteristics of a term appear for some scientists as a feature, for others - properties, for others - requirements. Often an equal sign was placed between these concepts. However, in our opinion, it is more expedient to talk not about requirements, but about the properties of terminology, since a requirement is a certain rule, a condition that must be fulfilled, and a property is "a side of an object that determines its difference or similarity with other objects and manifests itself in interaction with them" [Philosophical Dictionary, 1981. P.241].

A similar picture can be observed with the English term "guest", which in tourism is defined as "customer of a hotel or restaurant" [P. 141], while the word of the general literary language has the meaning "1) someone who is invited to an event or special occasion; 2) someone you have invited to stay in your home for a short time". To illustrate the implementation of the terminological meaning of the word "guest", use the following passage: "Most hotels in this price class have at least a boiler and some sachets for coffee and tea available for the guest" [Travel Daily News. September 29, 2009]. With the semantic development of the common meaning of the word "guest", the meaning narrowed from a more general one to one that is associated with the studied area of knowledge.

Generally, we can conclude that the authors of such lexicographic works are not philologists and terminologists, but subject specialists, as a rule, candidates and doctors of economic sciences. Moreover, these works do not always correspond to the generally accepted rules of lexicographic description and design; compilers are guided only by their own experience, which leads to a decrease in the quality of dictionaries. As a result, a comprehensive linguistic consideration of the term "tourism" and its comparative analysis in Uzbek and English is a prerequisite for creating a high-quality dictionary of tourist terms.

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